

Microwave-induced stereospecific synthesis of *trans* 3-phenylthio β -lactams

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Phenylthioacetyl chloride is a potential precursor of ketene in Staudinger reaction with imine in synthesis of stereodefined 3-phenylthio β -lactam derivatives. Herein we describe the reaction of imines with phenylthioacetyl chloride in the presence of N-methylmorpholine under microwave irradiation and classical condition. The reaction is highly stereospecific since only *trans* β -lactam is formed exclusively. This is an example in which identical products are formed under microwave irradiation method and thermal conditions.

Keywords: Microwave, stereospecific, thio- β -lactam, ketene-imine, Staudinger [2+2] cycloaddition.

Introduction

Staudinger [2+2] cycloaddition reaction of ketene and imine is one of most power tool in synthetic organic chemistry for the synthesis of β -lactams under thermal conditions¹. This is a classical reaction, a valuable method by Hermann Staudinger in 1907 for the synthesis of β -lactam antibiotics and their analogues²⁻⁴. The β -lactam ring is the key structural motif in most of the widely used antibiotics⁵⁻⁷. The increase of antibiotic resistant of pathogenic bacteria's has led to intense demand to develop the new and novel methods for the synthesis of antibiotics drugs molecules⁸⁻¹³. Over the past century numerous synthetic strategy has been developed for the β -lactam synthesis. For instance catalytic asymmetric kinugasa reaction¹⁴⁻¹⁶, metal carbene C-H insertion¹⁷, α -diazoketone under photochemical irradiation¹⁸⁻²⁰, ester enolate-imine condensation²¹ and radical cyclization are very crucial²²⁻²⁴.

Among these approaches, the Staudinger, ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction has proven the most versatile

method to construct the 2-azitidinone rings. This strategy is quite simple and effective for the synthesis of diverse densely functionalized β -lactams by the coupling of ketene and imine from easily accessible starting materials.

The stereochemical outcome of the reaction is difficult to predict normally because this reaction proceeds through stepwise manner and stereochemical assignment is elucidated based on torquoselectivity model²⁵. Further the stereochemical assignment of this reaction is supported by intensive research based on theoretical and experimental results²⁶⁻²⁸.

In spite of the above studies the stereochemistry of β -lactams has been greatly depend on the structure of ketene and imine counterparts, mode of addition of the reagents, nature of the solvents, temperature and the base used to generate the ketene during the course of the reaction^{29,30}. The nature of N-substitution has also effect on *cis* to *trans* β -lactam formation³¹⁻³³.

3-Phenylthio- β -lactam derivatives are potential synthetic

precursors. For example, they are employed in synthesis of various β -lactam derivatives viz. 3-halo³⁴, 3-alkyl³⁵, 3-alkoxy³⁶, 3-acyl³⁷ and 3-oxo- β -lactam³⁸, via different chemical transformation. In this paper, we report the synthesis of *trans* 3-phenylthio substituted β -lactam starting from diaryl imines and phenylthioacetyl chloride in presence of N-methyl morpholine under microwave irradiation. Interestingly, this reaction also produces the *trans* isomer at 50°C temperature. No *cis* isomers are formed.

Perhaps the effectiveness of this method is due to the fact that 1,2,3-trisubstituted β -lactams are prepared by this method. To enhance the speed of chemical reactions, the concept of microwave irradiation is introduced in organic chemistry more than 30 years ago^{39–41}. It is interesting to note that one of us (BKB) is also involved in β -lactam chemistry and microwave-induced science for the past three decades. In general, rapid microwave irradiation alters the stereochemical distribution of the product^{42–44}.

Results and discussion

This study on the stereochemistry is highly suitable and applicable to monocyclic β -lactams. For a comparative study of stereochemical results, conditions of the experiments must be the same with all substrates. β -Lactam synthesis is usually conducted by the addition of acid chloride to a solution of 1,2-substituted imine in the presence of triethylamine at cold conditions (0–5°C) to room temperature. Under these conditions, 1,2-diaryl imines with acetoxy, phenoxy, benzyloxy and methoxy acetyl chloride produced exclusively *cis* stereoisomer⁴⁵. In contrast, phthalimido acetyl chloride produced *trans* isomer in major proportion⁴⁶. An identical observation

was noted with 1,2-dialkyl, 1-aryl-2-alkyl or 1-alkyl-2-aryl imines with these acid chlorides. Importantly, crotonyl chloride and these types of unsaturated acid chloride did not yield any products at room temperature or cold conditions. However, at high temperature (in refluxing benzene), the products were mostly *trans* and a small proportion of *cis* isomer was formed with 1-aryl-2-alkyl or 1-alkyl-2-aryl imines. In contrast, crotonyl chloride-type of acid chloride gave *cis* β -lactam with N-alkyl-2-carbomethoxy, N-aryl-2-carbomethoxy, N-alkyl-2-methylketone, N-aryl-2-methyl ketone and imines that have conjugated structures at the C-2 position. Electron withdrawing groups at the nitrogen of the imines produced mostly *trans* β -lactams regardless of the substituent present in the acid chloride components. This was further supported by the fact that imines derived from multicyclic aromatic amines and aromatic aldehyde always produced *trans* β -lactams⁴⁷. However, conjugated imines derived from conjugated carbonyl compounds always produced *cis* beta lactams regardless of the other groups present in the imine or acid chloride. This observation confirmed that the substituent present at the carbon of the imine is the most crucial in controlling the stereochemistry of the β -lactam formation reaction through cycloaddition reaction.

Phenylthioacetyl chloride **1** reacted with diaryl imine **2a-e** in the presence of N-methyl morpholine at 50°C under microwave irradiation and produced exclusively *trans* β -lactam **3a-g** in 60–80% yield. The same reaction under thermal condition also produced *trans*-isomer **3a-g** exclusively (Scheme 1). It worthy to be noted that there was no *cis* β -lactams formed.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 3-phenylthio- β -lactam under microwave and thermal condition.

Conditions of the experiments

It was found that the conditions of the experiments in the current investigation have no influence in the stereochemistry of the β -lactam formation. For example, three conditions were used to prepare β -lactams through classical method. Racemic 3-phenylthio β -lactams was prepared when a solution of acid chloride is added to a solution of imine containing N-methylmorpholine in chlorobenzene for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then heated in an oil bath at 50°C. The same β -lactam was obtained when imine solution was added to acid chloride and base followed by heating. Again, the course of the β -lactam formation was not different when N-

methylmorpholine was added to a solution of acid chloride and imine. In the microwave irradiation, all reactants were mixed together and irradiated at medium power level for 5–6 min. In most of the other examples, these variations of the conditions of the reactions affected the enantioselectivity and diastereoselective of the products. In general, microwave irradiation method produced a mixture of β -lactams with a low percentage of the *cis* isomer. The current experiments confirmed that microwave irradiation and classical methods can give identical stereoisomeric products. But microwave method was faster, economical and required simple glass apparatus to perform the reactions.

Table 1. Scope of the reaction and result of *rac*-(+/-)-3-phenylthio- β -lactam synthesis

Entry	Imine	β -Lactam	Yield ^a (%)
1		75	
2		80	
3		70	
4		65	
5		60	

^aIsolated yield.

Scheme 2. Stereocontrol in β -lactam synthesis.

Mechanistic view points

The mechanism of β -lactam formation reaction was studied. However, it was difficult to explain the enantioselectivity and diastereoselectivity in many instances. The stereochemistry of the β -lactam formation depends on the substitution pattern of the imine, acid chloride, order of the addition of reagent, nature of the solvent, temperature and nature of the bases. It had been seen that *cis* β -lactam is the exclusive or major isomer if acid chloride is added slowly at cold to room temperature to a solution of imine and triethylamine. In contrast, a *trans* β -lactam was the main product if the base is added dropwise to the imine and acid chloride solution at high temperature. It was believed that reaction of the imine and acid chloride proceeds from the less sterically bulkier side of the ketene and this pathway immediately forms zwitterionic transition state.

Subsequently, a conrotatory ring closure gave mixture of *cis* β -lactams specially when aliphatic groups hooked to the N atom of the imine. Other possibilities of the isomerization of intermediate (I) along its C=N bond to give another zwitterionic intermediate (II) when N atom pre-occupied by the bulkier aromatic groups viz. phenyl, benzyl and substituted phenyl ring. The intermediate II underwent ring closure via conrotatory movement affords the corresponding *trans* 3-phenylthio- β -lactam as one of the sole products (3) (Scheme 2)^{29,48}.

Conclusions

Preparation of racemic *trans* 3-phenylthio β -lactams is performed under classical and microwave irradiation method. The stereochemical results are interesting because unlike many other similar processes this reaction produces products stereospecifically.

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